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on
RELEVANCE OF MODERN LIBRARIES
IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF RELIGION
CULTURE AND RESEARCH**

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Venue

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Article for National Seminar

Inbox

Dr. Krishna Kumar Kesharwani <kesharwani67@gmail.com> Thu, Mar 5, 7:04 PM
(3 days ago)

to P, jai, bcc: vivek

Dear Dr. P.S. Rajput

Good Evening

Find the attachment herewith for your reference and necessary action.

Thank you very much

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(DR. K. K. KESHARWANI)

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Dr. P S Rajput

to me

I am glad to inform you that **your paper has been accepted for presentation and publication in conference volume.**

Registered yourself

Thanks

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With Regards

Dr. P.S. Rajput

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INFLUENCE ON INFORMATION GATHERING HABITS OF INTERNET BY THE LIBRARY USERS IN THE INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY IN INDIA

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Abstract :

The user is focal point of all information systems to facilitate the transfer of information between two or more accessory, however distant from each other in space or in time. The general orientation and design of information systems are always sounded on user and should reflect his characteristics, attitudes, needs and demands. So in user studies, information on user characteristics should be included and well documented by the differences according to variables like age, nature of job, job environment etc. Reference group is the group with which a person psychologically identifies himself or in relation to which he think himself and think around him. Professional colleagues, friend's acquaintances, fellow professionals outside the department/ institution/ locality/ state/ country/ expert within the field all they will form 'reference group' of a private which may control an individual's habits, behavior, style and even activities. Demographic variables like age and sex are also very powerful factors of any individual's information seeking behavior. The present study solely based on Internet search by the users in the India Institute of Technology in India.

Keywords : Information Seekers, User Studies, Networking, Internet, Computer Technology, IIT and ICT.

Introduction :

Information technology has influenced the very nature of business, research industrial, IT and management of libraries. They are undergoing significant changes today not only in outlook but also in function, services, methods and techniques for collection development, processing and dissemination for information. The conventional found out of brick and mortar libraries that store information within a constrained physical space have given thanks to data centers that integrate data sources round the globe by way of networking. Libraries have not yet explored their potential to the full with the advancement in technology and its direct application to libraries. Business, IT and management libraries are becoming lean and agile libraries that streamline information supply. The pervasive nature of the web , including platform independent database connectivity is popping library portals more and simpler . So the library is a live agency to promote education. Professor Yashpal, Ex-Chairman, UGC, a leading scientist in his forward to INFLIBNET report has stressed " The role and growth of information and knowledge is faster than even before and still accelerating. There are enormous number of new development in both its applications and pure thought." He further added that the education and creative members of the society should have quick access to whatever is happening in their own country and the world over.

It is assumed that whole of the knowledge generated throughout the world is shared through the various type of publications such as books, magazine and journals. If it is true, a good substance of knowledge is not reaching to the students of IITs and colleges of the IITs are not in a position to purchase each and every published document, this handicap of purchasing the new arrivals is applicable to each and every institution. If we want to be at par with the international development, then a quick access to what is being done in the country and abroad must be established by removing all constrains of distance, language and other man-made barriers. So the real learning can be performed in the libraries. It, therefore, becomes essential for students to come closer to libraries to establish relation with the books. Library is the heart of the university and IIT's education. It is a treasure house of knowledge.

The adequate library services within such institutions were developed for raising the standard of higher education in the country. After independence high priority has been accorded to develop appropriate collections and also attention has been paid to provide necessary equipment to cope with the application of the modern technology. In pre independence era the universities and the IIT's college for years together in the country continued without adequate building, collection and organized services. In the beginning the collections were housed in some less used area within the custody of some caretaker clerical staff. A new light spread to these services. Then the libraries were realized as information services centers. For common purpose co-coordinated development (networking) of library and information centers is an urgent need of the nation. It will bring quality in services. Libraries will be able to work as centers for self directed learning, which in turn will be of full use of human resource. The library services should be expanded to reach every one in every condition. However, the exponential growth of information and demand for speed and accuracy have forced to implement automation in management of library services.

Historical Background of Indian Institute of Technology & Their Library in India :

The Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs) are a gaggle of fifteen autonomous engineering and technology – orientated institute of upper education established and declared as Institutes of National Importance by the Parliament of India. The IITs were created to coach scientists and engineers, with the aim of developing a talented workforce to support the economic and social development of India after independence in 1947.

In order of establishment, they are located in Kharagpur (1950: as IIT 1951), Mumbai (1958), Chennai (1959), Kanpur (1959), Delhi (1961; as IIT 1963) Guwahati (1994), Roorkee (1847; as IIT 2001), Ropar (2008), Bhubaneshwar (2008), Gandhinagar (2008), Hyderabad (2008), Patna (2008), Jodhpur (2008), Indore (2009) and Mandi (2009). Some IITs were established with financial assistance and technical expertise from UNESCO, Germany, the United States, Japan and the erstwhile Soviet Union. Each IIT is an autonomous university, linked to the others through a standard IIT Council, which oversees their administration. They have a standard admission process for undergraduate admissions, using the Joint entrance exam (popularly referred to as IIT – JEE) to pick around 8,000 undergraduate candidates a year. Postgraduate admissions are done on the idea of the GATE, JMET, JAM and CEED. About 15,500 undergraduate and 12,000 graduate students study within the IITs, additionally to research scholars.

IIT alumni have achieved success during a sort of professions. Most of the IITs were created in early 1950s and 1960s as the Institutes of National Importance through special acts of the Indian Parliament. The success of the IITs led to the creation of the Indian Institutes of data Technology (IIIT) within the late 1990s and within the 2000s. All IITs are autonomous universities that draft their own curricula, and they are members of LAOTSL, an international network of universities in Europe and Asia. LAOTSE membership allows the IITs to exchange students and senior scholars with universities in other countries.

Concept of Information Seeking Behaviour :

With the deluge of obtainable information, everyone needs information of accelerating variety. The information needs of a selected group of users and for a specific situation or organization are difficult to work out. There is not one simple system to cope up with all information needs (Mahapatra and Panda, 2001). According to Krikelas (1983), information-seeking behaviour refers to “any activity of a private that's undertaken to spot a message that satisfies a perceived need.” Mick (1980) observed that “information producing and information-seeking behaviour are closely linked and are the explanations why most information systems aren't better accepted as they fail to supply linkage between the 2 activities.”

Data Analysis of the Study :

The change in traditional document delivery services, from print to electronic, has happen very quickly, and libraries and knowledge services have undergone significant transformation so as to effectively deliver electronic resources to the academic community. Moreover, the rapid advancement of data Communication Technology (ICT) has brought a revolutionary change within the information scenario giving rise to variety of options to the users' community to handle varied information sources conveniently and effortlessly as a result of which e-resources have become the lively substance to the modern library's reserves in satisfying varied needs of students, teachers, and researchers with minimum risk and time.

Electronic resources are rapidly replacing print resources because the largest consumer of library and knowledge center acquisition budgets. Logically, organizations want to guage the usage of electronic resources and incorporate the results into their deciding regarding resource acquisition, licensing and termination (as well because the related allocation of other library resources including staff and physical space). The current process for assessing the usage of electronic resources for a given institution, however, is extremely complicated, time-consuming, and highly unsatisfactory.

The present article deals with the data, collected through two questionnaires administered to (i) Librarians and (ii) the Users of different IIT libraries. Statistics collected from the various records have been analysed as:-

➤ Library Network :

What is happening in one's own field or related field can not be known unless and until, he/she is well networked with other people who are associated in the field concern. Libraries provide an opportunity to each individual to know what is happening in user's area of study and for this library get networked with International/National or Local Network to share their sources with service users.

Data of Library Network

S. No.	Response	No. of Users	% of Users
1.	International Library Network	253	57.55
2.	National Library Network	297	66.00
3.	State Library Network	51	11.33
4.	Local Library Network	129	28.66

The data of the above table reveals that users are known about the library networking whether they are plugged with or not. 57.55% users say that their libraries are well concerned with international library/Networks, 66% users opinioned that their libraries are network with National Library Network, 11.33% users say that their libraries are associated with state library network 28.66% users are of opinion that their libraries are a part of a Local Library Network.

➤ **Purposes of Using Internet :**

To formulate the policy for acquiring the e-resources the librarian must understand the purposes of using the Internet by their users. In other words it should be known to the librarian whether the users use Internet for emailing, chat purpose or do they have some academic purpose. The librarian also must know the type of information the users seek from the Internet and the type of documents they access to fulfill their requirements for information needed for their study and research. Users were asked to elaborate their choice of documents they access while using the Internet. Responses have been analyzed in the given below Table.

Table : Data of Using Internet by Users

S. No.	Type of E-Information	No. of Response	Percentage
1.	E-Journals	159	35.29
2.	Downloading Services	153	34
3.	E-Articles	135	30.00
4.	Online Search	97	21.47
5.	E-Thesis and Dissertations	83	18.44
6.	Databases	54	12.00
7.	E-Books	48	10.66
8.	Newsgroups	27	6.00
9.	Mailing Lists	21	4.66
10.	Subject Gateways	12	2.66
11.	E-Archives	9	2.00

An analysis of the table shows that highest number of responses i.e. 159 accounting for 35.229% of total population use the Internet for accessing electronic journals followed by downloading services (34%, e-articles (30.00%), online search (21.47%), e-thesis and dissertations, databases (18.44%), e-books (10.66%) and so on. Further analysis also reveals that most of the respondents use the Internet for academic purpose not just for emailing for chatting.

Conclusion :

The study has covered all IIT Libraries and user study. It is found that, these library are doing fairly well by providing Online Resources and Services to their patrons and users. It has been felt that there is need to upgrade library technology and informational resources as in some cases library lacks proper facilities to access information resources. It is recommended that each IIT libraries should have a separate information technology cell to update their library resources, services.

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